

Islamic Financial Engineering Role in Combating Covid-19 Epidemic Issues: A Case Study of Pakistan

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Abstract

The world and Pakistani economies have suffered from COVID-19. MSMEs are the main victims of COVID-19. This paper evaluates the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) and offers policy recommendations to help them mitigate economic losses and navigate the crisis. Financial engineering integrates financial theory, engineering approaches, mathematics, and programming. Finance also involves using mathematical and computational methods to implement financial tasks. Islamic Financial Engineering (IFE) is crucial in the customer-driven derivatives sector, which involves quantitative modelling, programming, trading, and risk management of derivative products. The objective of the study is to explore whether the Islamic financial engineering contributes or not to resolve the issues of COVID-19 in Pakistan i.e: (a) to identify the important role of Islamic financial engineering toward COVID-19 Issues remedies in Pakistan (b) to identify the important role of IFE to combat COVID-19 issues in Pakistan (c) to explore more financial products to cover up the dent on poor people due to covid- 19 (d) to improve the role of Islamic microfinance institutions with the help of IFE tools to help the people get rid of poverty (e) to analyze policy implications under IFE and recommendation to accelerate in attaining the revival after COVID-19. The study focuses on the above discussed objectives by examining the performance of MSMEs during and after COVID-19 pandemic. A comparison is given to depict the main variables in these periods i.e prior - during and after COVID-19 pandemic till July 2021. Recommendations has given to the Government and regulators of financial and non-financial sectors to arm thm to cop ith such plausible issues in future.

Keywords: Islamic Financial Engineering, COVID-19, solutions, MSMEs, Pakistan

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